

Brain Tumour Charity	
Data management plan required?	Encouraged and dependent on award
RDM policy Link	No
Definition of data	Not specified
Length of data management plan	Not specified
DMP template/ requirements	Not specified
Required data repository	Not specified
Time for data release	Not specified
Time for long-term storage of data	Not specified
Costings	Not specified
Last updated	Not known
Contact Details	research@thebraintumourcharity.org
Comments	Member of AMRC. Clinical research training fellowships in partnership with MRC therefore see MRC guidelines. Brain Tumour Awards in conjunction with Cancer Research UK

Documents used:

Terms and conditions of awards for research grants.

https://assets.thebraintumourcharity.org/live/media/filer_public/d5/d2/d5d2ad2e-5ffe-41d4-be55-0a85a906ffa5/tbtc_grant_conditions_v9.pdf

Accessed: May 2018